

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ
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Introduction

Research practice is an integral part of the educational process and is important in the training of a qualified specialist. It is aimed at consolidating and deepening the knowledge and skills acquired by students in the learning process, as well as mastering the system of professional skills.

A brief description of nosology, why are you interested in it

Acute hematogenous osteomyelitis (AHO) is a common invasive infection encountered almost in the pediatric population. (Males are more affected than females, as they are more liable to trauma). While a number of pathogens may cause AHO, *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most common organism identified. The main symptom is inflammation but poor general condition also occurs occasionally. Elevation of CRP and sedimentation rate as well as leucocytosis are the most important laboratory findings. Conventional x-ray is mandatory, however scintigram and MRI are now specific in the early stage. Ultrasound can show abscess formation in the soft tissue. Treatment involves the immediate use of specifically targeted, intravenous antibiotics. Surgical intervention stands in second place. Immobilisation is only useful in the initial treatment of pain. Strict diagnostic and therapeutic management prevents complications, which would need reconstructive bone and soft tissue reconstruction, and is the key to a good primary prognosis.

I am interesting in because I am a boy, this disease happened several times during playing, and also my brothers .

The purpose of the research work:

To study nosology in order to ...

The overall aim of this project was to systematically review the literature on diagnostic imaging for osteomyelitis in order to identify the techniques with the best diagnostic accuracy and the greatest clinical utility, across the range of types of disease and patients.

The objectives of the research work: 1. Perform a systematic review of all studies reporting the diagnostic accuracy of any relevant imaging test, or combination of tests, used to detect osteomyelitis.

2. Perform diagnostic meta-analyses of identified studies to formally assess their diagnostic accuracy.

3. Investigate diagnostic accuracy across the range of different types of osteomyelitis and types of patient.

4. Compare the diagnostic accuracy of diagnostic tests both statistically and pragmatically, by systematically reviewing inter-rater reliability, and the broader implementation of imaging tests,

accounting for key factors such as availability of machinery, radiation exposure and acceptability to patients.

5. Provide useful guidance as to which imaging tests should be preferred.

5. preparation of a report on research practice

Acute Hematogenous Osteomyelitis

Acute osteomyelitis is almost a disease of children. (Males are more affected than females, as they are more liable to trauma).

Etiology:

- **causative organisms:** Usually *Staphylococcus aureus* (80%). Less often *Streptococcus pyogenes* or Gram negative *Haemophilus influenzae*.
- **Source:** septic focus e.g. Boils or IV lines.
- **Route :** the blood .

Pathology:

Site:

1. **In adults, hematogenous** infection is more common in the vertebrae (especially thoraco lumbar).

2. **In children.** the lesion is almost always in the **metaphysis of long bones**, most often at the lower end of femur, upper end of tibia.

• **This predilection for the metaphysis is due to :**

1. The peculiar arrangement of blood vessels (supplied by end arteries).
2. Most liable to trauma.
3. It is the actively growing end of bone.
4. Attachment of ligaments and muscles to it (subjected to strain).

Natural history of osteomyelitis :

1. Inflammation and suppuration :

There is congestion and exudation. By the second or third day, pus forms within the bone causing intense pain and obstruction of blood flow.

2. Extension and bone necrosis (Sequestration) : The extension may be:

(a) Horizontal spread : Results in the formation of subperiosteal abscess. Later, the abscess may open on the skin with resultant discharging sinuses.

(b) Vertical extension : Along the medulla may result in thrombosis of the major nutrient vessels and massive sequestration of the shaft.

• **The sequestrum** is smooth, shiny white, and devoid from periosteum and so gives a metallic sound on percussion by a probe. Separation of a sequestrum is known by probing (it moves) and by X-ray where

a black hollow is seen surrounding the sequestrum which is dense.

3. New bone formation in two sites :

(a) The deep layers of the stripped periosteum by the end of 2nd week.

With time the new bone thickens to form an **involucrum** enclosing the sequestra.

If the infection persists, pus may continue to discharge through perforations

(cloaca) in the involucrum and sinuses to the skin surfaces,

the condition is now established as a chronic osteomyelitis.

(b) Around the Haversian canals resulting in bony sclerosis.

4. Resolution :

The bone around the zone of infection is at first osteoporotic, later there is sclerosis and thickening of the bone. Remodelling may restore the normal contour.

Complications of acute osteomyelitis :

Systemic: Metastatic infection (pyemic abscesses).

Local:

1. Suppurative arthritis.
2. Altered bone growth.
3. Chronic osteomyelitis.
4. Pathological fracture.

Clinical features :

1. Type of patient : **usually child**
2. Severe limb **pain, malaise** and **fever**.
3. The earliest sign is severe **localized tenderness** over the inflamed part of the bone.
4. Later, there is **warmth, edema** and the skin is **red**.

5. Although any **movement** of the limb is **painful, the neighbouring joint can be moved passively and there may be an associated effusion.**

Investigations :

1. Laboratory: Leucocytosis, raised ESR and blood culture may be positive.

2. X-ray : Is normal during the first two weeks, then rarefaction and periosteal new bone formation appear. **Treatment should not be delayed while waiting for these to appear.**

3. Radioscintigraphy : With ^{99m}Tc-HDP (hydroxymethylene diphosphonate) reveals increased activity in the very early stage.

4. The most certain way to confirm the clinical diagnosis is **aspiration of pus. s. MRI :** can detect osteomyelitis before the appearance of radiological changes in plain radiology.

Differential diagnosis :

1. Cellulitis .

2. Acute suppurative arthritis. Tenderness is over the joint and all movements are painful & limited.

3. Rheumatic arthritis.

4. Hemarthrosis.

5. Ewing's sarcoma.

Treatment:

1. Supportive treatment: for pain and dehydration.

2. Splintage : of the affected part.

3. Antibiotic therapy :

The core of treatment : is early administration of high-dose IV antibiotics that are effective against staphylococci. Start with flucloxacillin intravenously or second generation cephalosporin & gentamycin for 3 or 4 days, then once the condition begins to improve, oral antibiotics are prescribed for another 3-6 weeks.

4. Surgical drainage :

Indication : If the patient is first seen after 48 hours or if there is no good response to antibiotics within 2 days

Method:

- Done under general anaesthesia and under a tourniquet.
- The inflamed area is explored; the periosteum is opened to evacuate the pus which is sent for culture and sensitivity.

- Some surgeons advise drilling of the cortex to evacuate any pus in the medullary cavity.

After care:

1. Splintage is continued until the inflammation subsides and the X-ray shows that there is no risk of a pathological fracture.
2. Full weight bearing is usually possible after 3 - 4 weeks.

A medical case 1

A 16-year-old Arabian male presented to our emergency department with a complaint of new-onset dyspnea and left hip pain with gait disturbance that started 1-week ago after a fall on his hip last week. The patient works as a car mechanic and his history included a recent urinary tract infection (UTI) with no further information regarding the clinical course and treatment of the condition. Hip X-ray was reported normal, and the Chest X-ray, which showed bilateral infiltrations, was presumed to be community-acquired pneumonia (Fig. 1). The patient was discharged on Levofloxacin. After 2-days the patient returned with worsening dyspnea, a 39 °C fever, and persistent left hip pain. The patient was admitted to our hospital. On admission, his respiratory rate was 24 breaths/minute, his SpO₂ was 88% on ambient air with tachycardia (110 beats/minute).

chest X-ray for the patient on admission showing bilateral pulmonary infiltrates (red circles). Arrow refer to bilateral pulmonary infiltrates.

Chest examination showed increased tactile fremitus in the right lung lower lobe, diffuse fine crackles in both lungs, and dullness to percussion on the right lung lower lobe. Left lower limb examination showed pan-edema, warm skin, and limited range of motion in both hip and knee joints.

Lab results showed respiratory failure with inflammatory response and elevated thrombotic markers. His hemoglobin was at 9.2 g/dL, white-cell count 35,000/ μ L, Neutrophils 87%, ESR 145 mm/hour, creatinine 2.1 mg/dL, Sodium 127 mmol/L, potassium 3.08 mmol/L, Ferritin 918 ng/dL, D-dimer 2850 ng/mL. Arterial blood gas indicated a pH of 7.52, SpO₂ 89%, PO₂ 54, PCO₂ 28, and HCO₃⁻ of 21 mEq/L. Laboratory results are summarized in Table 1.

Variable	Reference range	On admission	One month later
Hematocrit%	36.5-52.0	31.1	28
Hemoglobin, g/dL	12.0-17.4	9.2	8.3
White cell count	3.5-10.0	35	12.3
Neutrophils	40-70	87	77
Lymphocytes	22-44	9	16
Red cell count	4.00-5.50	3.45	3.25
MCV	27.0-32.0	70.5	84
Platelets count	150-400	180	1418
ESR, mm/hour	0-22	145	140
CRP, mg/L	0-5		134
Creatinine	0.6-1.4	2.1	0.15
Urea, mg/L	Aug-50	134	17
Sodium	135-145	127	137
Potassium	3.4-5.00	3.08	4.4
ALT, μ /L	Oct-55	41	172
Alkaline phos.	30-300		106
LDH WI	Less than 248		268
Ferritin	12-300	918	918
Iron	60-170		25
D-Dimer	Less than 500	2850	
pH	7.37-7.42	7.52	
CO ₂	35-45	28	

LDH Lactate dehydrogenase, *ALT* Alanine transaminase, *MCV* mean corpuscular volume, *ESR* Erythrocyte sedimentation rate, *CRP* C-reactive protein

Non-contrast chest CT revealed right lower lobe opacity and diffuse nodular opacities in both lungs (Fig. 2). Computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CT-PA) identified rounded nodular opacities in both lungs most of which are cavitory with the largest measuring 4 cm, with no evidence of massive pulmonary embolism.

Computed tomography scan of the patient's chest showing right lower lobe opacity with diffuse nodular opacities and cavitation in both lungs

Doppler ultrasound of the left lower limb shows Knee strain and left femoral vein thrombosis. Blood cultures were drawn later after admission, and the patient was initially started on Enoxaparin and empiric antibiotic treatment with Ceftriaxone, Vancomycin, and Levofloxacin. Later, Blood cultures, along with bronchoalveolar lavage fluid cultures grew fluoroquinolone-sensitive extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. All antibiotics were discontinued and meropenem was started.

The patient's limb clinical symptoms were consistent with deep vein thrombosis (DVT), which was confirmed by ultrasound findings. Additionally, bilateral pneumonia with a confirmed cavitary lesion and suspected emboli were observed on CT-PA. The presence of positive blood and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid culture results further suggested the presence of septic pulmonary embolism (SPE).

Further evaluation through transesophageal echocardiography revealed a normal heart and valves with no vegetation. Based on these findings, the diagnosis of SPE associated with DVT caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was made.

After 2 weeks of treatment with meropenem, the patient's respiratory status remarkably improved but he remained persistently febrile.

In light of these findings, an abscess was suspected, and a complete re-evaluation was started.

Laboratory investigation showed minimal improvement with almost similar values to the ones on admission (Table 1).

Whole body scanning computed tomography was performed. Chest CT showed remarkable regression of lung opacities compared with the previous one on admission. Left hip joint CT showed a hypodense transverse lesion with a non-regular border on the intertrochanteric line that extends to the hip joint, indicating a fracture (Fig. 3). In addition, there was rich loculated effusion inside the joint that is suspicious of an abscess.

Left hip joint computed tomography showing a hypodense transverse lesion with a non-regular border on the intertrochanteric line that extends to the hip joint, indicating a fracture

Contrast MRI of the left hip joint showed traumatic bone marrow edema in the neck and body of the femur and a 13–18 mm loculated effusion in the joint that extended to the medial and lateral parts of the femur body with an extended joint capsule (Fig. 4). MRI and CT findings were highly suggestive for osteomyelitis with subsequent abscess formation.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the hip joint showing bone marrow edema in the femur bone with joint effusion

The patient underwent an exploratory operation for the left hip joint, during which an abscess was detected, consequent drainage resulted in abundant pus exudate, and cultures grew fluoroquinolone-sensitive ESBL *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. In addition, a fracture of the anterolateral part of the femoral neck was confirmed.

How did it end?

The patient was discharged with a prescription of oral Ciprofloxacin and IV Cefoperazone-Sulbactam for 4 weeks as blood and joint drainage fluid cultures grew fluoroquinolone-sensitive ESBL *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Additionally, the patient was given non-weight-bearing instructions and physical therapy for the left hip joint. After discharge, the patient was examined on multiple occasions, and the lab workup showed normal ESR and CRP levels. However, the

clinical examination of the hip joint showed joint stiffness and reduced mobility. As a result, the patient was referred to orthopedic specialists and underwent hip joint replacement surgery.

A Medical case 2

A previously healthy 18-month-old boy presented at the emergency department with left hip pain and a limp following a minor trauma. His mother reported that he had presented fever for three days, cough and rhinitis about 15 days before the trauma, and had been treated with ibuprofen for 7 days (10 mg/kg dose every 8 h, orally) by his physician. The child presented with a limited and painful range of motion of the left hip and could not bear weight on that side. Examination of the other joints was unremarkable, and no inflammatory signs were evidenced. Blood tests were performed and showed white blood cell (WBC): 23,000 cells/ μ L; neutrophils: 86%, C-reactive protein (CRP): 7.2 mg/dL; erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR): 52 mm/h. Blood cultures were taken at admission, before administration of antibiotic therapy, and yielded negative results. Ultrasound scan of the hip was normal. X-rays of the pelvis and left hip showed a lytic lesion of the proximal femoral metaphysis.

(Figure 1)

X-rays of the pelvis. Osteolytic lesion of the proximal metaphysis of the left femur (arrow).

The child was admitted for suspected acute osteomyelitis of the proximal femur and a Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) was ordered. The gadolinium-enhanced MRI confirmed the clinical suspicion of osteomyelitis (Figure 2). After orthopedic consultation, a closed needle biopsy, and drainage of the lesion was performed. Specimens were sent for histological and microbiological examination and empiric intravenous (IV) antibiotic treatment with ceftazidime and oxacillin was started. Specimen cultures grew methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA). The child showed rapid clinical improvement, and normalization of inflammatory markers.

(Figure 2)

MRI confirms osteomyelitis of the femoral neck with a possible involvement of the growth plate without involvement of the joint cavity (arrow). (a) T1-weighted image showing metaphyseal fluid collection with surrounding edema; (b) T1-weighted SPIR image enhancing the fluid component.

How did it end ?

After 7 days, intravenous therapy was stopped and replaced with oral flucloxacillin (25 gm/kg every 6 h) for an additional 4 weeks. Six months after discharge the child showed clinical improvement and reached pain-free full range of motion of his left hip. Gait was normal, as well as blood tests, and X-rays findings.

A medical case 3

A 65-year-old man presented to our clinic with exquisite low back pain. The patient stated he had been potting plants a few days before this episode of low back pain. The patient described the pain as a generalized low back pain that became sharp pain with any movement or positional change. The patient also noted the pain intensity was preventing him from sleeping. Lumbar spine orthopedic/neurological examination revealed a severe reduction in range of motion and palpable tenderness over the lumbosacral spine. The neurological examination was unremarkable. Physical examination revealed a low-grade fever of 99.5°F. The remainder of the examination was limited because of pain. A plain film examination of the lumbar spine showed moderate to severe degenerative joint and degenerative disk disease at all levels and a loss of the normal curve (Fig 1). The clinical impression was acute lumbago secondary to advanced degenerative changes with secondary muscle spasms. Persistent pain and a low-grade fever 6 days after the initial evaluation and treatment prompted a referral for a lumbar spine magnetic resonance image (MRI) to rule out osteomyelitis; however, no known predisposing factors for vertebral osteomyelitis were ever identified in the history.

Fig 1. Plain film radiographs of a 65-year-old man with low back pain. Osteomyelitis is only detectable on plain film if the infection has been present for more than 1 to 2 weeks. Degenerative disease can mask more serious underlying spinal pathology. A, Anteroposterior

lumbar spine radiograph shows degenerative disk disease at multiple levels. B, Lateral lumbar spine radiograph shows disk space narrowing and osteophytes present at multiple levels.

A lumbar spine MRI was obtained with and without contrast in both the sagittal and axial planes. The MRI revealed a loss of signal through the vertebral bodies of L2 and L3, which crossed the disk space (Fig 2). This low-signal region increased in signal on T2 and enhanced significantly after injection of contrast. An enhancing lesion was also identified posterior to L3 and in the paravertebral musculature greater on the left than on the right. This was described as being most consistent with an epidural abscess and a psoas abscess. The epidural abscess significantly narrowed the sagittal diameter of the thecal sac at the level of L3 (Fig 3, Fig 4). The diagnostic impression was osteomyelitis and discitis across the L2-3 disk space with epidural abscess posterior to L3 and a paravertebral abscess.

Fig 2. A, T1-weighted sagittal MRI. B, T2-weighted sagittal MRI. These nicely show the classic appearance of vertebral osteomyelitis. The classic presentation of vertebral osteomyelitis is infiltration of two adjacent vertebral bodies and the intervertebral disk space. An epidural abscess is present posterior to L3 (arrow).

Fig 3. A T2-weighted axial MRI shows an abscess in the right and left psoas muscles (arrows). The epidural abscess significantly narrows the central canal and effaces the thecal sac (arrow heads). Neurological complications may develop secondary to an epidural abscess. Radicular signs, muscle weakness, and/or paralysis suggest the presence of an epidural abscess.

Fig 4. Magnetic resonance imaging is the imaging technique of choice in diagnosing and evaluating vertebral osteomyelitis. In addition to detecting osseous lesions, MRI can evaluate the bone marrow, the paravertebral soft tissues, and any epidural or spinal cord lesions. Axial T2-weighted MRI shows high signal intensity in the L2-3 disk space and right and left psoas muscles. An epidural abscess is seen effacing the thecal sac and narrowing the central canal (arrow).

The patient was referred for medical management. Subsequently, computed tomography (CT)-guided fine needle aspiration was performed (Fig 5); the specimen was cultured and tested positive for *Staphylococcus aureus*. The diagnostic impression was spontaneous vertebral osteomyelitis. The L2-3 level was surgically debrided and fused after a regimen of antibiotic therapy.

Fig 5. Computed tomography has the ability to detect vertebral osteomyelitis much earlier than plain film radiography. Computed tomographic scan of a 65-year-old man with vertebral osteomyelitis shows end-plate destruction of the L3 vertebral body.

Treatment

The primary goals in the treatment of vertebral osteomyelitis are as follows: first and most important is making the right diagnosis, identifying the organism, eradication of the infection, prevention of neurological complications, maintaining spinal stability, and adequate nutrition to promote recovery and rehabilitation.

Proper identification of the organism is accomplished by biopsy, blood cultures, or both. Once the organism has been identified, proper antibiotic therapy can commence. An antibiotic is selected based on culture and sensitivity. The typical course of therapy involves 2 to 6 weeks of parenteral antibiotics. Once objective clinical improvement occurs, the ESR and CRP begin to normalize, or if resolution of the infection is detectable via imaging, the patient can then be converted to oral antibiotics.

The natural history of treated vertebral osteomyelitis is ankylosis of the involved vertebral segments; however, indications for surgical management of vertebral osteomyelitis are obtaining a biopsy sample, drainage of an abscess, treating a neurological complication, maintaining spinal structural stability (usually via spinal fusion in cases of severe bony destruction), or failure to respond to appropriate antibiotic therapy.

Although the infection is active, spinal immobilization and bed rest will aid in pain relief and preventing spinal deformity.⁶ However, once there is objective evidence that the infection has been eradicated, spinal stabilization should progress from passive care to active care. In addition,

fighting the infection is likely to shift the patient into a catabolic metabolism.¹⁶ Therefore, nutritional management should be focused toward shifting the metabolism back into an anabolic state. Generally, a diet with a high protein intake, a moderate amount of carbohydrates, and a low fat intake supplemented with the essential amino acids will bring the patient back into a state of positive nitrogen balance.

Conclusion

Acute osteomyelitis almost in children is a serious disease that, when detected and treated early, can heal without severe sequelae . It is of primary importance to recognize the signs and symptoms at the onset of the disease and to properly use the available diagnostic tools . The role of serum markers as predictive factors for diagnosis has not been completely established. In particular, PCT should be further evaluated in larger studies and a cut-off value has not been univocally defined.

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